

Myopia Progression and the Spleen's Role: An Integrative Interpretation through Traditional Chinese Medicine.

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Abstract

Myopia, a refractive condition of increasing global prevalence, is traditionally addressed by Western medicine through factors such as excessive screen use and limited exposure to natural light. This review explores the influence of the Spleen on myopia progression from a Traditional Chinese Medicine perspective, presenting a complementary and holistic view. According to Traditional Chinese Medicine, the energetic imbalance of the Spleen, caused by factors like excessive studying, exaggerated worry, inadequate diets (cold, processed, and sugary foods), and exposure to cold, compromises the production of Blood (*Xue*) and its circulation. These factors generate dampness and phlegm which, by making the blood more viscous and causing inflammation, impair the nutrition and oxygenation of the eye's microvessels. The deficiency of Blood and poor circulation directly affect the nutrition of the ocular muscles, contributing to the axial elongation of the eyeball, one of the main factors of myopia. Traditional Chinese Medicine offers strategies aimed at strengthening the Spleen and the *Xue*, harmonising the energetic system to improve overall *Xue* circulation and, consequently, ocular health.

Keywords: Myopia; Cold; Muscles; Spleen; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Stress; Diet.

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1. Introduction

The prevalence of refractive errors, namely myopia, has been increasing significantly over the years ¹. The conventional approach points to poor dietary habits and the constant use of electronic devices, such as computers, tablets, and mobile phones, as the main factors in the development of this condition ^{2,3}. In Traditional Chinese Medicine, this view is acknowledged but is complemented by the exploration of internal factors, given that the body is understood as an integral system, where the imbalance of one part affects the whole ^{4,5}.

Curiously, the progression of myopia does not follow a strictly linear logic (where 1+1=2). The cause and development of myopia raise important questions, such as the fact that not all individuals who spend long hours in front of screens develop the condition ⁶. If the use of screens were cited as the primary and exclusive cause for the increase in myopia in the global population, one would expect all intensely exposed individuals to require optical correction, or conversely, that children who frequently play outdoors would be immune to these refractive errors ⁷. These inconsistencies leave a significant space for new perspectives.

Therefore, this research aims to explore the relationship between myopia and the Spleen in Traditional Chinese Medicine, analysing how the energetic imbalance of this organ can manifest in ocular refraction and influence the progression of myopia, with a special emphasis on *Xue* circulation and nutrition.

2. The Connection of the Spleen to Ocular Health in Traditional Chinese Medicine

In Traditional Chinese Medicine, ocular health is directly linked to the balance of various organs, with the Liver being the most commonly associated. Myopia is a condition that arises from Liver *Xue* deficiency or Liver or Kidney *Yin* deficiency, considering that the basis of *Yin* is *Xue* and that the Liver only stores and distributes it. Therefore, it makes perfect sense to focus treatment on improving the quality of the *Xue*⁸. The Spleen plays a fundamental role, as it is primarily responsible for the digestion and assimilation of food, generating the “pure essence” (*Gu Qi*) that is the basis for the formation of *Xue*⁹. A deficient Spleen compromises the production of *Xue* and its circulation⁹, which affects the nutrition of the entire body, including the eyes. Additionally, the Spleen is considered the “governor of the muscles,” being responsible for their nutrition and tone⁹. Axial myopia, characterised by the elongation of the eyeball^{10,11}, is a structural change that is under the influence of the Spleen, as the Spleen is responsible for structural changes⁹, indicating a direct connection between its imbalance and the progression of myopia. Organ prolapse, such as the uterus and stomach, is also associated with Spleen *Qi* deficiency^{9,12}, which reinforces its influence on the support of bodily structures, including the ocular musculature.

3. Factors of Spleen Imbalance and the Impact on Circulation

Various factors of modern life weaken the Spleen and the *Xue*, with a direct impact on *Xue* circulation.

3.1. Cold and Inadequate Diet

The Spleen prefers warmth for effective digestion. Exposure to cold (whether environmental or through cold and raw foods and drinks) depletes the Spleen's *Yang Qi*, slowing down the digestive process and causing stagnation of *Qi* and *Xue*^{9,13}. Cold causes the contraction of muscles and blood microvessels^{9,12}, hindering the supply of nutrients and oxygen to the eyes. In this regard, evidence indicates a sharp increase in myopia in winter compared to summer^{14,15}.

3.2. Educational Pressure and the Impact on Myopia Progression

The Spleen is the “residence of thought” (*Yi*). Excessive studying and mental pressure consume the Spleen *Qi*, leading to the depletion of *Xue*^{9,12}. There is a higher prevalence of myopia in urban areas compared to rural areas. A study conducted on young Jewish adults attending Orthodox schools in Israel shows that the prevalence of myopia (81.3%) and high myopia (20.4%) are as high as those observed in young adults in East and Southeast Asia (where educational pressure is quite high and their students rank at the top of international assessments), with these rates being much higher compared to those of young people attending secular schools in Israel¹⁵. The prevalence of myopia is generally lower in rural areas, especially those with less access to education¹⁵.

3.3. Diet Rich in Sugars and Processed Foods

The consumption of refined sugar weakens the Spleen, promoting the accumulation of dampness and phlegm⁹. High blood sugar levels increase blood viscosity and make circulation difficult in microvessels. These factors can impair the nutrition and oxygenation of ocular structures. A molecular mechanism that may be related to this lack of oxygen was described in a scientific article, “The role of retinal histone lactylation in myopia” development shared by the journal *Cell Metabolism*. If the eye does not have enough oxygen (hypoxia), this increases how it processes sugar. In other words, when there is little oxygen, the cells of the sclera begin to use more sugar for obtain energy, creating a by-product called lactate^{16,17}.

3.4. Worry, the Emotion that Imbalances the Spleen

Worry is the emotion that consumes the energy of the Spleen¹⁸. When we are in a state of "pre-occupation," our brain, which consumes a significant amount of *Xue*, becomes exhausted trying to solve or control every situation we wish to avoid. In the same way that the Spleen has the function of controlling and holding all the body's structures in place, it also attempts to control situations or potential events. The Spleen is intrinsically linked to the need for control, and this dominance can generate chronic stress^{18,19}. The attempt to control and predict events can, in turn, give rise to other feelings, such as fear, irritability, or frustration, which ultimately generate stress that is highly inflammatory for the body. Stress hormones (such as cortisol and adrenaline) cause the Liver to release more glucose (sugar) into the bloodstream, as the body is preparing for a "fight-or-flight" situation and needs rapid energy¹⁹. If the stress is constant, these sugar levels can remain elevated, exhausting the energy of the Spleen, which will constantly attempt to regulate these levels in the bloodstream. The excessive stimuli we are exposed to today by living in urban areas, the educational pressure imposed on us, and professional competitiveness are factors that generate significant stress²⁰.

4. Therapeutic and Preventive Approaches of Traditional Chinese Medicine

Traditional Chinese Medicine offers a range of interventions to strengthen the Spleen and improve circulation, mitigating the progression of myopia.

4.1. Acupuncture

The treatment aims to tonify *Qi* and nourish *Xue*. The following points are frequently used²¹:

- **Bladder 20 (*Pishu*, Figure 1):** Used to powerfully strengthen the Spleen and promote its function of transformation and transportation of nutrients, thereby increasing the production of *Qi* and *Xue*.

Figure 1. Bladder 20 localisation according to the World Health Organization²².

- **Bladder 17 (Geshu, Figure 2):** Known as the Influential Point of the *Xue*, it is used to invigorate and harmonise the *Xue*. Since the eye relies on sufficient Blood for nutrition, this point is crucial.

Figure 2. Bladder 17 localisation according to the World Health Organization ²².

- **Spleen 4 (Gongsun, Figure 3):** Harmonises the Stomach and regulates the Penetrating Vessel. It is particularly effective at eliminating facial oedema or swelling. This action improves circulation in the face, which makes it a point of great importance for controlling the progression of myopia.

Figure 3. Spleen 4 localisation according to the World Health Organization ²².

- **Spleen 6 (Sanyinjiao, Figure 4):** This point is vital as the meeting point of the three Leg Yin channels (Spleen, Liver, and Kidney). It powerfully nourishes *Xue* and *Yin*, making it essential for systemic nutrition, which directly benefits ocular tissues.

Figure 4. Spleen 6 localisation according to the World Health Organization ²².

- **Gallbladder 39 (Xuanzhong, Figure 5):** Influential Point of the Marrow. As the Marrow is strongly linked to Blood production, this is a fundamental point in cases of Liver *Xue* Deficiency, important for structural stability.

Figure 5. Gallbladder 39 localisation according to the World Health Organization ²².

- **Governing Vessel 20 (*Baihui*, Figure 6):** An essential point for ascending the Spleen *Yang* and directing *Qi* and clear energy to the head and face, positively influencing ocular health.

Figure 6. Governing Vessel 20 localisation according to the World Health Organization ²².

4.2. Herbal Medicine

In herbal medicine, *Ginkgo biloba* is a valuable strategy, especially in winter, as its action in tonifying the *Xue* and improving blood circulation helps combat viscosity and stagnation caused by the cold ²³. For issues of stress and nervousness, the formula *Yang Xin Ning Shen Wan* can be used to nourish the Heart and *Xue* and calm the mind ²⁴.

4.3. Diet Therapy and Lifestyle

This approach emphasises maintaining a balanced and easily digestible diet while avoiding cold, raw, processed, and sugary foods that may impair digestive function and *Qi* circulation. From a traditional Chinese medicine perspective, such foods can weaken the Spleen and contribute to internal dampness or stagnation ²⁵. In parallel, stress reduction through practices such as *Qigong* and *Taijiquan* is considered essential to regulate emotional balance, harmonise the flow of *Qi*, and promote mental calmness ²⁶⁻²⁹.

5. Conclusion

Myopia can be seen by Traditional Chinese Medicine as a manifestation of a systemic imbalance with a strong influence from the health of the Spleen. The weakening of this organ, induced by factors such as cold, mental stress, and diets rich in sugars, compromises the production and circulation of *Xue*. This poor circulation, characterised by viscosity and inflammation, impairs the nutrition and oxygenation of the eye, contributing to the axial elongation of the eyeball. Traditional Chinese Medicine may offer an integrative approach that complements the Western approach, emphasising the importance of strengthening the Spleen to prevent and manage the progression of myopia.

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